

**SIMULATION AND CONTROL
OF A FILAMENT WINDING MACHINE
WITH HEATING DEVICE FOR THERMOPLASTIC PREPREGS**

J. ATANGANA ATEBA*, S. AIVAZZADEH*, G. VERCHERY**

*Lab. Mechanics of Composites and Joints
Institut Supérieur de l'Automobile et des Transports (ISAT)
19, rue de l'Oratoire,
58000 NEVERS, FRANCE

**Materials and Mechanical Engineering Department
Ecole des Mines de Saint-Etienne
158, Cours Fauriel,
42023 ST ETIENNE CEDEX 2, FRANCE

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a software (PC-fil2.0) for simulation and control of a filament winding system including a heating device. This system is currently developed as an extension to thermoplastic impregnated fibres of a prototype filament winding machine with controlling software. The heating device is designed with two degrees of movements to follow the placement of the fibre thermoplastic prepreg on to the mandrel. The existing software running on a microcomputer previously limited to four degrees freedom, was extended to seven degrees to incorporate the control of the heating head. It generates data for programming the control unit and also provides the user with simulation facilities, to visualize the process. The present version of the PC-fil2.0 is available for revolution vessels of general shape.

Keywords : Filament Winding, Feed-Eye, Revolution Structures, Fibre-Path, Control, Simulation, Thermoplastic Fibre Composites, Heating Path, Heating Point.

1. INTRODUCTION

The advantages of the filament winding process to manufacture vessels, specially revolution bodies, are well known (Peters et al ¹) :

- large structures can be built ;
- cost can be reduced with the high productivity obtained in the fast fibre lay down ;
- high quality can be achieved, due to the use of continuous fibres, the high repetitivity in the fibre placement, the low void level.

Presently this technique is mostly limited to thermosetting resin, and the use of the thermoplastic fiber-composites in the winding technique is not widespread. However in addition to the classical advantages given above, thermoplastic matrices appear to offer certain major attractions, such as :

- suppression of the impregnation process of roving,
- potential of easy and rapide fabrication,
- lowest cost than classical winding process,
- higher damage tolerance.

A research for simultaneous winding and curing of thermoplastic yarns is now in progress at ISAT. and Ecole des Mines, based on previous development of research filament winding system including equipment and software, and is described in the present paper.

2. GENERAL PRESENTATION OF THE SYSTEM

The filament winding system used in our research is composed of three main parts :

- a filament winding machine,
- a numerical control unit,
- a micro-computer with a special software.

The filament winding machine is a prototype specially built for research purpose. It was initially designed as a 3-axis machine (El Nahas ², 1991) with rotation of the mandrel, and longitudinal and transverse movements of the feed-eye. In the present research, it is planned to upgrade it to 7 axes, as described below, extending the control of the feed-eye movement and incorporating the control of a heating device.

The numerical control unit is an industrial modular unit, able to control up to seven axes. It uses its own low-level programming language. It can be programmed directly from its keyboard or can be loaded with externally prepared data and programmes through a RS-232 interface. For complex sequences, direct programming reveals too complicated and external preparation of control programmes is necessary.

The micro-computer (IBM/PC AT type) is used to prepare data and programmes for the numerical control unit. A first version of the software has been developed previously for a 4-axis machine, including the rotation of the feed-eye around a longitudinal axis as the 4th axis (Abdelhady et al ^{3,4}, 1988, 1989). In the present research, this software has been extended to control 7 axes. The software generates the data used to load the numerical control unit. It also produces a graphical simulation of the process on the colour video display of the micro-computer.

3. DESIGN OF THE MACHINE

The purpose of the device in development is to heat the reinforced thermoplastic filament at the very point of deposit on the mandrel. The heating source (its nature is not yet defined, and can be laser or IR beam, or blowtorch) has to follow the point of deposit, remain at a definite distance of the mandrel and preferably orthogonal to it. These specifications lead to two types of design. With the classical control of filament winding, due to the rather complex path of the feed-eye for general forms, the point of deposit is not always in the same meridian plane. Consequently, the heating device requires three movements : two for traveling in a meridian plane and the third for tilting that meridian plane. This design was first considered in our research ; more information is given in Atangana et al ⁵ (1992). However, it appears that in such a design, the rotation of the heavy crossbeam supporting the heating device around the mandrel axis, necessary to follow the deposit point when the radius of the mandrel varies, requires powerful motors and can be a source of vibrations. Another design can meet this difficulty, with a fixed crossbeam to support the heating head, two translations in the meridian plane for the heating head, and a vertical degree of freedom added to the feed-eye movement. This extra motion is to enforce the deposit point to lie in the meridian plane of the crossbeam supporting the heating device. Such a motion of the feed-eye involves less inertial effects than the tilting of the crossbeam. Including a rotation of the feed-eye, this design comprises 7 degrees of freedom. Figure 1 gives a schematic presentation of the machine design, which is currently in its final development. 1 is the micro-computer, 2 the numerical control system, and 3 the filament winding machine with its seven controlled motors : $M(X_O)$ for the longitudinal translation of the feed-eye, $M(Y_O)$ for the transversal translation of the

feed-eye, $M(Z_0)$ for the vertical translation of the feed-eye, $M(\alpha)$ for the rotation of the feed-eye in the domes, $M(X_1)$ for the longitudinal translation of the heating head, $M(Z_1)$ for the vertical translation of the heating head, $M(\theta)$ for the rotation of the mandrel.

Figure 1 : Seven-axis thermoplastic filament winding machine controlled by micro-computer.

4. THE CONTROL PROGRAMME

4.1. Analysis

Three positions are of interest : the feed-eye location F, the contact point M at which the fibre takes off the mandrel, and the heating head H (Figure 2). Figures 2-A and 2-B present the significant geometrical parameters on the mandrel. Figure 2-C shows the position of the fibre in the current tangent plane to point of deposit M.

Figure 2 (A, B, C) : Geometrical parameters.

The position of the feed-eye is X_0 on the longitudinal axis Ox , Y_0 on the transverse axis Oy and Z_0 on the vertical axis Oz . The position of the heating point is X_H on the longitudinal axis Ox , and Z_H on the axis Oz . S is the parallel at point M . The meridian γ is the meridian in the vertical plane. The angle between the fibre and γ at a cross section of mandrel in M is ψ . The rotation angle of the mandrel is θ . R is the radius of the mandrel at point M and R' is the derivative with respect to x of R at the same point (Equation 4). The parameter λ in the Equations (3) is the length of the fibre FM . β is the angle between the tangent plane $\pi(M, N, N')$ to the mandrel at point M and the horizontal plane. This angle is zero when the radius R is constant. F is located on π (Figure 2-C).

In the present machine, the feed-eye lies in the horizontal plane $Z_0 = 0$ and is consequently defined by its coordinates X_0 along the mandrel axis and Y_0 . The fibre is tangent to the mandrel at the contact point M . This completely determines its coordinates X_M , Y_M , Z_M and the radius R of the vessel in the contact cross section, as function of X_0 , and Y_0 . For the last modifications, the depositing point M is located on the upper meridian of the mandrel and its coordinates are :

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_M &= X \\
 Y_M &= 0 \\
 Z_M &= R
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

The heating head H, assigned to remain in the contact cross section at a fixed distance d from the contact point, is then defined by its cartesian coordinates :

$$\begin{aligned} X_H &= X_M \\ Y_H &= 0 \\ Z_H &= R + d \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The feed-eye position F is defined by its cartesian coordinates X_o , Y_o and Z_o such as :

$$\begin{aligned} X_o &= -X + \frac{\lambda \cos \psi}{\sqrt{1 + R'^2}} \\ Y_o &= \lambda \sin \psi \\ Z_o &= R + \frac{\lambda R' \cos \psi}{\sqrt{1 + R'^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In which :

$$R' = \frac{dR}{dx} = \tan \beta \quad (4)$$

4.2. Programming

The PC-fil2.0 is developed on an IBM / PC compatible micro-computer with graphical features. The software permit to control the following parameters (Figure 2) :

- 1 - the mandrel rotation (θ),
- 2 - the longitudinal movement of the feed-eye (X_o),
- 3 - the transverse movement of the feed-eye (Y_o),
- 4 - the vertical movement of the feed-eye (Z_o),
- 5 - the longitudinal movement of the heating device (X_H),
- 6 - the vertical movement of the heating device (Z_H),
- 7 - the rotation of the feed-eye around a horizontal axis (α).

The PC-fil2.0 is written in Turbo-BASIC. The previous version has been extended to include the determination of the parameters defining the heating device movements and that of the feed-eye control new version, according to the analysis outlined above. A simulation of the heating head trajectory has been added too.

The program generates a file in which the parameters necessary to the numerical control unit are stored. When operating the machine, this file has to be loaded in the control unit through the RS-232 interface.

4.3. Simulation:

The basic program has been modified. Presently, we can determine the control parameters of the feed-eye (X_o , Y_o , Z_o), the mandrel (θ), and the heating point (X_M , Z_M), as shown in Figure 2. The simulation example presented in Figure 3 is for a combination of two spherical domes connected by a cone and two cylinders. The Figure shows three curves :

- curve (A) is the feed-eye path ; 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 1', 5' indicate the successive positions of the feed-eye for a round trip ;
- curve (B) is the mandrel pattern ; 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 indicate the successive positions of the point M where the fiber takes off ;
- curve (C) is the heating path ; 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 indicate the successive positions of the heating point M.

Figure 3 : Feed-eye and heating paths,
for two spherical domes connected by a cone and two cylinders.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a software for simulation and control of a filament winding system with a heating device, developed for manufacturing revolution vessels in thermoplastic fibre composites. This software controls seven parameters, of which five are used for the controlled placement of the fibre with a deposit point in a prescribed meridian plane, and two for the motion of the heating device in this plane. A graphical representation of the motions and fibre placement provides the user with a convenient simulation of the whole process. The software generates data subsequently loaded in a numerical control unit which controls the machine.

It is planned in the future to develop a direct control of the system from the micro-computer with a convenient extension of the present software.

6. REFERENCES

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